

Bayesian-Optimized Multimodal Neural Network and its Application in the Mechanism and Data Dual-Driven Digital Twin of PWR-Core

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ABSTRACT

The mechanism-data dual-driven approach has emerged as a representative development direction for digital twins and an effective solution for realizing digital twins of nuclear reactor cores. Nevertheless, the effective utilization of the substantial measured data from nuclear power plants to achieve reliable data-driven functionality remains a critical challenge. In order to address the challenges posed by data fusion in the context of multi-source heterogeneous monitoring data from the core, which includes both one-dimensional scalars and spatially distributed signals, this paper proposes a multimodal neural network architecture. It employs a branched structure to process different types of core status parameters separately and incorporates a dynamic weighting network for adaptive feature fusion. In order to enhance network performance, a Bayesian optimization method is innovatively introduced to achieve automatic and intelligent hyperparameter tuning. Based on the BEAVRS benchmark, the validation process demonstrated that the neural network in question successfully achieved online dynamic correction of measurement uncertainties in operational condition parameters. The results show that the optimized network reliably reduces the L_2 norm between predicted values and ground truth to below 0.1, thereby substantiating the efficacy and preeminence of the proposed multimodal neural network in enhancing the mapping accuracy of core digital twins.

Keywords: Mechanism-Data Dual-Driven

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital twins have been identified as a pivotal technological framework for achieving the profound integration of cyber-physical systems[1]. By constructing a high-fidelity virtual mapping of physical entities, it provides closed-loop support for smart manufacturing systems, encompassing real-time perception, dynamic prediction, and decision-making optimization. Currently, this technology has been widely applied across various fields, including aerospace, power systems, and automotive manufacturing, significantly enhancing operational efficiency and safety levels[2-4].

In the domain of nuclear power, inherent drivers such as technological advancement and the transition towards smart manufacturing are imposing progressively stringent requirements on the safety and economic performance of Nuclear Power Plants (NPPs). The reactor core, which serves as the primary source of energy generation, is distinguished by its intricate nature, the challenge in direct measurement of critical parameters, and the implementation of exceptionally stringent safety standards. Consequently, digital twin technology demonstrates significant application potential in this domain. This technology facilitates more precise reconstruction and facilitates understanding of the internal physical fields within the core. Thus, it provides essential support for enhancing the safety and economics of nuclear power.

At present, digital twin solutions for nuclear reactor cores can be divided into two broad categories: purely data-driven and mechanism-data dual-driven approaches. The fundamental principle of data-driven solutions is the construction of surrogate models, utilizing techniques such as neural networks

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and reduced-order models based on core operational data and core structural data, with the objective of facilitating the prediction of critical core parameters[5]. In contrast, mechanism-data dual-driven solutions leverage the computational accuracy of physics-based models and enhance their precision with data-driven approaches within an acceptable computational efficiency. This integrated solution facilitates a more precise mapping of the internal physical fields within the reactor core, yielding logically self-consistent physical field parameters that are readily available for subsequent analysis and application[6].

The implementation of either digital twin solution is fundamentally dependent on vast amounts of measured core parameters from NPPs. These measurements originate from a variety of monitoring systems, including:

- (1) The ex-core neutron flux monitoring system, which used for continuous measurement of total reactor power and core axial power offset.
- (2) The secondary loop heat balance system, which used for determining the reactor's thermal power.
- (3) The in-core instrumentation system, which used for measuring the core power distribution and calibrating the ex-core system.
- (4) In-core detectors, which used for continuous monitoring of the intra-core power distribution.
- (5) Elbow flow meters, which used for measuring the primary coolant flow rate.
- (6) Resistance temperature detectors, which used for measuring the primary coolant temperature at the core inlet and outlet.
- (7) Thermocouples, which used for measuring the coolant temperature at the top of the core active zone.
- (8) Boron meters, which used for measuring the boric acid concentration in the primary coolant.
- (9) The control rod position monitoring system, which used for tracking control rod insertion depths.

Collectively, these parameters provide comprehensive monitoring of the core's internal state. In consideration of the heterogeneous nature of the data structures and formats acquired from these disparate systems, it is imperative to leverage the characteristics inherent in this multimodal data during the construction of the neural network.

In accordance with the background, the background, Section 2 of this paper describes the physics-data dual-driven digital twin framework for the Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) core. Subsequently, Section 3 details the construction of a data-driven framework and a multimodal neural network, utilizing extensive measured data from the nuclear power plant. Bayesian methods are employed for intelligent hyperparameter optimization of the network. The accuracy is evaluated in Section 4 through modeling of the *BEAVRS* benchmark. The overall performance and a comprehensive discussion are provided in Section 5.

2. MECHANISM-DATA DUAL-DRIVEN DIGITAL TWIN FRAMEWORK FOR THE PWR-CORE

The construction of the multimodal neural network in this work is based on the physics-data dual-driven digital twin core framework proposed by Xi'an Jiaotong University[7]. The fundamental premise of this methodology encompasses three sequential closed-loop feedback mechanisms:

- (1) **High-Precision Modelling:** A high-precision digital virtual core is constructed based on reliable mathematical-physical models, with no empirical corrections employed. The core's design parameters, such as manufacturing, assembly, geometric, and material parameters, are utilized in this process. This model has been demonstrated to accurately compute core status parameters (e.g., radial assembly power distribution within the core) and operational calculation parameters (e.g., power level, in-core detector response currents).
- (2) **Online Correction:** The utilization of online acquired core status parameters, operational calculation parameters, and operating measurement parameters facilitates the online correction of

operating condition parameters (including control rod positions, core coolant inlet temperature, and boron concentration), thereby eradicating their measurement uncertainties.

(3) **Accurate Computation:** The corrected operating condition parameters are then used as inputs to drive the high-precision digital core model, ultimately yielding accurate and reliable core status parameters.

As illustrated in *Figure 1*, the digital twin solution of PWR core in this study comprises two core steps. Firstly, in the mechanism-driven component (Step 1), a high-precision digital virtual core is constructed based on reliable mathematical-physical models. Secondly, in the data-driven component (Step 2), a neural network is utilized to online correct the measurement uncertainties of the operating condition parameters. The outcome of this process is a digital counterpart that maintains a credible twin relationship with the physical reactor core.

Figure 1 Mechanism-data dual driven digital-twin framework for PWR-core

For the physics-driven component, the core physics analysis software NECP-Bamboo is employed, which developed by the NECP laboratory at Xi'an Jiaotong University[8-10]. The software under discussion offers comprehensive capabilities for core physics analysis and fuel management, thereby enabling accurate monitoring of global core parameters. The critical strength of the model lies in its multi-physics coupling, which enables the simultaneous handling of whole-core neutron diffusion, thermal-hydraulics, nuclide depletion, criticality search, and detector response. This facilitates full-cycle reactor simulation. It is important to note that this software does not rely on any empirical correction factors and incorporates a generalized cross-section parameterization module. This provides users with the flexibility to customize parameterization forms.

The construction of the mechanism-driven component is based on the BEAVRS benchmark. The validation encompasses critical parameters from both the start-up physics tests and the power operation periods, including critical boron concentration, temperature coefficients, control rod worth, and radial assembly power distribution within the core. The errors associated with all calculation results have been verified in prior work and are confirmed to be within the acceptable limits[11].

3. DATA DRIVEN COMPONENT OF DIGITAL TWIN FRAMEWORK FOR THE PWR-CORE

The fundamental concept of the data-driven component acknowledges that inevitable systematic and measurement errors introduce uncertainties into measured data. Therefore, the construction of a neural network is proposed for the purpose of mapping from core status parameters, operational calculation parameters, and operating measurement parameters back to the operating condition parameters. This process is intended to result in the dynamic elimination of measurement uncertainties.

The data flow of this component is illustrated in *Figure 2*. Specifically, when core status parameters at state S_0 are acquired from the target physical core, the component automatically performs parameter sampling within the measurement uncertainty ranges of the operating condition parameters. This process yields a set of samples that collectively encompass the uncertainty domain. The samples are

then processed through a single model calculation (which incurs a time cost of t_m) to generate the database required for the neural network. Following the execution of the correction by the neural network (at a cost of t_d in terms of time), the uncertainty-corrected operating condition parameters are yielded. Subsequently, these rectified parameters are employed as the model's input once more. The final model calculation is then executed in order to obtain the refined core status parameters.

Figure 2 Data flow of data driven component

Figure 3 Framework of multimodal neural network

The proposed framework is capable of utilizing substantial amounts of real-time measurement data acquired from the physical target core, thereby eliminating error propagation caused by core measurement uncertainties in the mechanism-driven model. It provides crucial support for achieving high-precision mapping from the physical target to the digital twin core and ensures their online synchronization. The subsequent section will provide a comprehensive elaboration of the process of constructing the neural network based on the generated dataset to obtain the refined operating condition parameters.

3.1. Database

The neural network developed in this study is trained on data derived from operational calculation parameters generated by NECP-Bamboo, following sampling within the measurement uncertainty ranges of the operational condition parameters. The components of the operating condition parameters vector X are elaborated below, with the BEAVRS benchmark serving as a case in point.:

- (1) The Measurements of control rod position are typically averaged from several sensors. Due to factors such as mechanical wear, neutron irradiation damage, and electromagnetic interference, the measurement error for a single sensor can reach ± 10 steps[12].
- (2) Core Coolant Inlet Temperature is generally measured using thermocouples. In intense radiation fields, thermoelectric drift coupled with potential sheath fouling introduces a systematic error of approximately ± 0.5 °C.
- (3) Primary Coolant Boron Concentration usually obtained through offline calibration, this method suffers from significant time lag and chemical analysis deviation, resulting in a measurement uncertainty of about ± 2.5 ppm[13].

Uniform sampling was performed within the uncertainty interval for each parameter mentioned above, with sample sizes set at 21, 11, and 21, respectively. A Cartesian product of these parameters was taken to generate the measured sample set X_n , covering the joint uncertainty domain of the operating condition parameters. Using X_n as input to the mechanism-driven component, the corresponding core operational calculation parameters Y_n (including relative power, in-core detector response current, and Axial Offset (AO)) were calculated. This process ultimately formed a compensation database $\{(X_n, Y_n), n = 1 \sim 4851\}$ containing 4851 sample pairs for training the neural network.

3.2. Multimodal Neural Network

Figure 3 presents the schematic of the constructed multimodal neural network architecture. A modular feature extraction design is employed in order to handle the structurally complex operational computed parameters in the database.

In the context of one-dimensional scalar data, such as relative power and axial offset, the deployment of a fully connected network is a common practice. The model employs a pyramidal structure for dimensionality reduction, incorporating Dropout layers to prevent overfitting.

For the purpose of analyzing spatially distributed detector current data, a deep convolutional network is applied in accordance with the standard "Convolution-Activation-Pooling" paradigm. The branch utilizes 5x5 kernels to capture initial spatiotemporal features, followed by 2x2 kernels for refined extraction. The number of channels increases progressively, forming a hierarchical feature representation space.

The Mish activation function is employed throughout these feature extraction processes due to its smoother gradient, which better aligns with the gradual transition characteristics of core state parameters. Normalization is performed within each channel. Furthermore, the AdamW optimizer is adopted in the network, which is designed to address overfitting more effectively by decoupling weight decay, thereby enhancing the model's generalization capability and training stability.

In the feature fusion stage, a dynamic weighting network is introduced. This network autonomously learns the importance weights for features from different branches based on the input data, thereby enabling an intelligent fusion strategy.

During the multi-target regression optimization phase, the weighted and fused features are concatenated and passed through a final fully connected layer. This layer maps the features to a three-dimensional output space through three successive dimensionality reductions, yielding the final prediction.

3.3. Training Strategy and Analysis of Hyperparameter Space

As illustrated in *Figure 4*, the training of the neural network follows a specific sequence of steps. After the loading of data, the application of standardized processing to each branch is initiated with the objective of mitigating the impact of parameter scale differences on the network.

During the training phase, the system automatically determines whether hyperparameter optimization is required. In the absence of such a configuration, the final training is conducted directly using default parameters. In instances where optimization is required, the hyperparameter space is initially delineated to ascertain the parameters that require tuning. These include the number of hidden neurons in the power branch, the AO branch, and the detector current branch; the dropout rate; the learning rate; the training batch size; and the weight decay coefficient of optimizer.

A Bayesian optimization approach is employed to identify a set of hyperparameters well-suited to the neural network architecture within this defined space. In order to provide the Bayesian optimizer with a sufficient initial sample, five random hyperparameter sets are first generated, and their corresponding validation losses are obtained. The Bayesian optimizer is then utilized to identify the optimal combination of hyperparameters, thereby achieving the lowest possible validation loss.

The performance of each hyperparameter set is evaluated using k-fold cross-validation (with k=5). The training set is then divided into five equal parts, with each part utilized sequentially as the validation set, while the remaining four parts are employed for training purposes. The mean validation loss across all five folds is employed as the performance metric for a given hyperparameter set. As demonstrated in *Figure 5*, the number of training epochs for cross-validation is set to 300, at which point the training loss has generally converged to a stable state.

Following the identification of the optimal hyperparameter set, the model undergoes final training on the complete training dataset. In order to facilitate the comprehensive learning of the data features by the model, the dropout rate is set to zero during this final training stage.

In order to ensure that the value ranges of various parameters within the hyperparameter space remain reasonable, a preliminary analysis was conducted on the key hyperparameters. To illustrate this point, consider the example of batch size. As demonstrated in *Table I*, with other hyperparameters fixed, the

final prediction deviation and training time after 300 epochs were compared for different batch sizes. Following a thorough evaluation of the available data, it was determined that the optimal batch size range is between 128 and 512. The selection was primarily based on the observation that this range yielded relatively low prediction deviation, and a batch size of 512 offered reduced training time compared to 256 while maintaining comparable accuracy. A similar analytical methodology was employed to define the final search ranges for the hyperparameters, the results of which are outlined below. The batch size was varied from 128 to 512, the dropout rate from 0.1 to 0.4, the learning rate from $1.0E-2$ to $1.0E-4$, and the weight decay coefficient from $1E-3$ to $1E-6$. The number of hidden neurons for the power branch, the AO branch, and the detector current branch all span from 128 to 1024.

Figure 4 Training strategy of multimodal neural Network

Figure 5 Training loss and validation loss variations under a set of hyperparameter combinations

4. Analysis of the Neural Network Accuracy

It is evident that the training process has culminated in the successful development of a multimodal neural network with Bayesian-optimized hyperparameters. This network has the capacity to execute online, dynamic correction of the measurement uncertainties associated with operating condition parameters based on measured core status parameters.

In order to validate its performance, a case from the BEAVRS benchmark was investigated, specifically at a burnup depth of 38.7 MWd/tU in the first cycle. A total of ten random samples were extracted from within the measured uncertainty ranges of the operating condition parameters. The corresponding core status parameters from these samples were entered into the neural network, which then produced the corrected operating condition parameters. The findings indicate that the $L2$ norm between the predicted values and the ground truth can be reduced to below 0.1 following *Bayesian* hyperparameter optimization, thereby substantiating its efficacy in achieving high-precision mapping.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The present paper methodically expounds on the conceptualization, optimization, and validation of a multimodal neural network for a physics-data dual-driven digital twin of a PWR-core. As the critical component of data-driven, the network effectively integrates multimodal monitoring data from the reactor core through its unique architectural design and employs Bayesian optimization for intelligent hyperparameter tuning. The validation results demonstrate that the neural network exhibits excellent online correction capability, significantly reducing the effect of measurement uncertainties in operational condition parameters and stabilizing the $L2$ norm of key prediction metrics below 0.1 from previously higher levels. This work not only confirms the crucial role of the data-driven component within the overall framework, but, more importantly, presents an efficient and automated approach for neural network construction and optimization, offering a transferable solution to data uncertainty

challenges in nuclear power plants. The future work will further integrate measured data from nuclear power plants, thereby advancing the development of a mechanism-data dual-driven digital twin reactor core.

Table I Analysis of Parameter Ranges in Hyperparameter Space. The "base" line represents the true reference values of the prediction targets. The remaining columns present the results obtained by adjusting only a single specified hyperparameter, including the predictions, training time, training loss, and the L2 norm between the predictions and the ground truth.

Parameters	value	CR/cm	Tin/K	BC/ppm	Time/s	train loss	L2
base		383.93250	568.608	639.179			
Batch size	32	384.25058	568.6127	639.2243	2353.7	0.000890	0.37
	64	384.29633	568.6089	639.2238	1014.2	0.000972	0.41
	128	384.1185	568.6122	639.2197	568.6	0.001160	0.23
	256	383.72964	568.6126	639.2154	220.4	0.001375	0.24
	512	383.70663	568.6103	639.2209	176.4	0.001800	0.27
Dropout rate	0.1	384.1185	568.6122	639.2197	568.6	0.001160	0.23
	0.2	384.0648	568.6097	639.2191	512.0	0.001161	0.17
	0.3	384.08865	568.6126	639.2183	514.7	0.001161	0.20
	0.4	384.12143	568.6126	639.2185	512.4	0.001159	0.23
Learning rate	1.0E-02	384.12833	568.6339	639.2792	522.0	0.000828	0.32
	1.0E-03	384.1185	568.6122	639.2197	568.6	0.001160	0.23
	1.0E-04	383.8997	568.6187	639.2032	524.8	0.002854	0.07
	1.0E-05	379.8507	568.6375	639.163	521.2	0.059980	4.13
Weight decay coefficient	1.0E-03	384.11578	568.6124	639.2198	518.5	0.001167	0.23
	1.0E-04	384.1185	568.6122	639.2197	568.6	0.001160	0.23
	1.0E-05	384.12802	568.6126	639.2198	525.0	0.001163	0.24
	1.0E-06	384.08917	568.6111	639.2191	516.8	0.001162	0.20
Scalar hidden	128	383.77045	568.61	639.2212	531.4	0.001154	0.21
	256	383.8155	568.6133	639.22	528.6	0.001142	0.16
	512	384.12796	568.6126	639.2208	524.2	0.001160	0.24
	1024	384.15594	568.6105	639.2242	517.0	0.001183	0.27
Detector hidden	128	384.1185	568.6122	639.2197	568.6	0.001160	0.23
	256	384.08878	568.6073	639.2272	545.3	0.001115	0.21
	512	384.27264	568.6095	639.2247	544.4	0.001062	0.39
	1024	384.0651	568.6106	639.2164	549.8	0.000965	0.17
AO hidden	128	383.7743	568.6101	639.2207	510.4	0.001203	0.20
	256	383.76508	568.6144	639.2097	536.0	0.001144	0.20
	512	384.12164	568.6155	639.207	539.3	0.001038	0.22
	1024	384.15884	568.6128	639.2072	526.4	0.000980	0.26

Table II Verification of Neural Network Accuracy in 38.7 MWd/tU of BEAVRS C1

num	status	CR/cm	Tin/K	BC/ppm	L2
	base	281.38566	563.303	789.121	
1	Random	271.35125	562.179	791.548	13.59
	correct	271.3544	562.1782	791.5493	0.01
2	Random	265.66691	562.617	787.499	18.03
	correct	265.68463	562.6077	787.4717	0.05
3	Random	292.91367	564.222	790.056	13.38
	correct	292.86142	564.2473	790.0568	0.08
4	Random	281.32581	563.811	789.287	0.73
	correct	281.29834	563.814	789.2877	0.03
5	Random	270.96038	564.788	790.272	13.06
	correct	270.96564	564.783	790.2722	0.01

6	Random	267.60829	564.655	788.802	15.45
	correct	267.53897	564.6616	788.8015	0.08
7	Random	276.63348	562.162	787.678	7.34
	correct	276.62137	562.1541	787.6852	0.03
8	Random	266.47345	563.348	786.786	17.29
	correct	266.47287	563.3356	786.751	0.05
9	Random	278.54278	561.858	791.185	6.35
	correct	278.4836	561.8539	791.1801	0.07
10	Random	290.14951	562.902	791.323	11.37
	correct	290.1523	562.8923	791.2766	0.06

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Tao, Q. Qi, L. Wang, and A. Y. C. Nee, "Digital Twins and Cyber-Physical Systems toward Smart Manufacturing and Industry 4.0: Correlation and Comparison," *Engineering*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 653-661, 2019/08/01/ 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eng.2019.01.014>.
- [2] E. Deri, C. Varé, and M. Wintergerst, "Development of Digital Twins of PWR Steam Generators: Description of Two Maintenance-Oriented Use Cases," in *2021 28th International Conference on Nuclear Engineering*, 2021, vol. Volume 1: Operating Plant Challenges, Successes, and Lessons Learned; Nuclear Plant Engineering; Advanced Reactors and Fusion; Small Modular and Micro-Reactors Technologies and Applications, V001T01A002, doi: 10.1115/icone28-63246. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1115/ICONE28-63246>
- [3] S. Li et al., "Key technologies and applications of Digital Twin hydraulic engineering," *Digital Twin*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 2486862, 2025/01/02 2025, doi: 10.1080/27525783.2025.2486862.
- [4] X. Chen et al., "Real-time refinery optimization with reduced-order fluidized catalytic cracker model and surrogate-based trust region filter method," *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, vol. 153, p. 107455, 2021/10/01/ 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2021.107455>.
- [5] W. Xiao, X. Liu, J. Zu, X. Chai, H. He, and T. Zhang, "Operator inference driven data assimilation for high fidelity neutron transport," *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 430, p. 117214, 2024/10/01/ 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2024.117214>.
- [6] X. Su, Z. He, Y. Huai, P. Luo, X. Jin, and D. Nie, "Exploration of Mechanism-Data Dual-Driven Digital Twin Application in the Huang River Tunnel," *Water Resources Informatization*, no. 1, pp. 21-27, 2025, doi: 10.19364/j.1674-9405.2025.01.004. (in Chinses)
- [7] Y. Li, Y. Liang, Y. Li, Y. Zhou, and L. Cao, "Mechanism-Data Dual-Driven Digital Twins Method for Nuclear Reactor Core," Patent CN120317139A, 2025-07-15.
- [8] Y. Li et al., "Development and verification of PWR-core fuel management calculation code system NECP-Bamboo: Part I Bamboo-Lattice," *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 335, pp. 432-440, 2018/08/15/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2018.05.030>.
- [9] W. Yang, H. Wu, Y. Li, J. Yang, and L. Cao, "Development and verification of PWR-core fuel management calculation code system NECP-Bamboo: Part II Bamboo-Core," *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 337, pp. 279-290, 2018/10/01/ 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2018.07.017>.
- [10] Y. Li, T. He, B. Liang, H. Wu, J. Bai, and J. Yang, "Development and verification of PWR-core nuclear design code system NECP-Bamboo: Part III: Bamboo-Transient," *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 359, p. 110462, 2020/04/01/ 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2019.110462>.
- [11] Y. Liang et al., "Validation of the PWR-core physics analysis software NECP-Bamboo based on NPP measurements," *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, vol. 181, pp. 105634-105634, 2025.. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2025.105634>.
- [12] P. Shen, et al. "Research on Harmonic Parameterization Method". *Atomic Energy Science and Technology*, vol 58(7):1452-1458, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.7538/yzk.2023.youxian.0836>. (in Chinese)
- [13] B. Jiang, et al, "Comparison Study of Boron Detection Method in Boron-Containing Wastewater of Nuclear Power Plant". *Nuclear Power Engineering*, vol. 40, no. 2, p. 95, 2019-04-15 2019, doi:10.13832/j.jnpe.2019.02.0095.